

Design and Implementation of a Smart Infrastructure Digital Twin

Didem Gürdür Broo^{1,2,3}, Miguel Bravo-Haro¹, Jennifer Schooling¹

¹ Centre for Smart Infrastructure and Construction, Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, CB3 0FA, Cambridge, UK.

² Laing O'Rourke Centre for Construction Engineering and Technology, Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, CB3 0FA, Cambridge, UK.

³ Centre for Digital Built Britain, University of Cambridge, CB3 0FA, Cambridge, UK.

Abstract

There is a critical need to make infrastructure systems more efficient, resilient, and sustainable. Infrastructure systems provide the basis for everyday life and enable the flow of goods, information, and services within urban and regional settings. Providing data-centric solutions to improve this flow is essential. This can only be achieved if we manage to transform passive infrastructure assets into cyber-physical systems. Digital twins bring the opportunity to turn passive infrastructure assets into data-centric systems of systems.

This article aims to provide a summary of existing digital twin architectures and exemplify a digital twin design and implementation. To this end, a literature review of digital twin architecture is presented in addition to a case study of a digital twin implementation in smart infrastructure. The case study focuses on a digital twin implementation of a bridge and describes in detail the physical, cyber, integration, and service layers of this implementation. Later in the article, we discuss the learnings from this case study under three main categories – systems perspective, information perspective, and organisational perspective. The findings show the importance of acquiring a systems perspective when designing digital twins today to enable interoperable systems of systems in the future. Furthermore, the findings highlight the vital necessity of data and information management while also considering the multidisciplinary aspects of digital twin design and implementation.

Keywords: data, digital twins, infrastructure, smart infrastructure, resilience.

1. Introduction

The term “digital twin” was introduced by Michael Grieves in 2003, (Grieves & Vickers, 2017). Since then it has experienced a growth in popularity and is now recognised as a key enabler for transformation to Industry 4.0. In the last two decades, many digital twin applications have been presented in the space (Glaessgen & Stargel, 2012) and manufacturing (Qi & Tao, 2018; Schleich et al., 2017; Tao et al., 2018) industries. A digital twin in the built environment domain has been defined as a realistic digital representation of assets, processes, or systems (Bolton et al., 2018). It mirrors physical, social, and/or economic systems and the processes that are articulated alongside the system in question, and across its lifecycle, mimicking its operation in real-time (Batty, 2018).

There are different approaches to implementing digital twins. While some researchers such as Rudrappa (2017) choose to provide digital twin classifications such as digital twin prototypes, digital twin instances, digital twin aggregates, and digital twin environments, others divide the digital twins into different categories due to their functions as status twin, operational twin or simulation twin (XMPRO, 2019). Digital twins can consist of several components such as models, data streams coming from the Internet of Things (IoT), sensors, data models, artificial intelligence and machine learning-enabled analytics and algorithms, and knowledge bases (Rudrappa, 2017). When combined with information and communication technologies and powerful data analytic algorithms such as artificial intelligence, digital twins allow organisations to conserve physical resources during design and perform diagnostic and predictive analyses during operations (Grieves & Vickers, 2017).

At this moment in time of digital twin developments, there is an urgent need to make infrastructure systems more efficient, resilient, and sustainable. Infrastructure systems provide the basis for everyday life and enable the flow of goods, information, and services within urban and regional settings (Rice et al., 2010). Providing data-centric solutions to improve this flow is essential. This can only be achieved if we manage to transform passive infrastructure assets into cyber-physical systems. Cyber-physical systems (CPS) are seen as the products of the fourth industrial revolution and comprise the integration of computation, networking, and physical processes with feedback loops where physical processes affect computations and vice versa (E. A. Lee & Seshia, 2016).

One way to turn physical assets into cyber-physical systems is through digital twins. Digital twins provide an opportunity for this transformation by enabling the acquisition and integration of data for improving the design, construction, operation, and maintenance of physical infrastructure assets which, in turn, could improve sustainable

development and shape a better future (Bowers et al., 2018). This study focuses on the cyber-physical systems perspective of digital twins and aims to provide knowledge on how to design and implement a digital twin for smart infrastructure using today's tools and technologies, and will consider the benefits and challenges. Therefore, the main research question of this article is:

RQ 1: How can we design and implement digital twins for smart infrastructure?

To answer this question, we have divided it into three sub-questions (SRQ):

- SRQ1: What are the relevant existing reference architectures that can be used in digital twin development for smart infrastructure?
- SRQ2: What are the important considerations during the design and implementation phases of digital twins in smart infrastructure?
- SRQ3: How should the software and data be architected for operationalising digital twins in smart infrastructure?
- SRQ4: What are the non-technological aspects that affect the development and adoption of digital twins in smart infrastructure systems?

The original contribution of this paper consists of an overview of digital twin architectures through a literature review. Then, the most promising digital twin architecture is selected to be tested with a case study. The article describes this case study, design, and implementation decisions and provides discussion on several tools and technologies related to the development of the digital twin.

To this end, Section 2 presents the methodology. The literature review is presented in Section 3, where the related work on digital twin implementation is presented in the first subsection, and the detailed literature on digital twin architectures to answer the SRQ1 are presented in the second subsection. Section 4 details the selected reference architecture. Later in Section 5, the smart infrastructure case study is described, the physical and cyber part of the system is detailed, and the system architecture of the digital twin is presented in Section 5. The answers for the remaining three research questions (SRQ2, SRQ3, and SRQ4) are answered in Section 6 where we discuss important considerations and challenges from systems, information, and organisational perspectives. Finally, we summarise the results of this study and conclude the article in Section 7.

2. Methodology

The study presented in this article follows two main methodologies. A literature review methodology is used to identify relevant literature to answer the first sub research question (SRQ1) on understanding the existing reference architectures that can be relevant to be used in digital twin development for smart infrastructure. To identify relevant literature keywords; such as “digital twin architecture”, “digital twins”+” architecture”, “digital twin”+” architecture”, “digital twin reference architecture” and similar, are used. Later, the results are read firstly only by checking the abstracts of the articles to find out the relevancy and secondly by reading the articles and identifying the important aspects of the proposed architectures.

The second methodology used is the case study methodology. Case study methodology had a long history across several disciplines since the early 1900s. It was quickly accepted as a useful methodology that assisted researchers in making acceptable interpretations from events outside the labs (Gürdür, 2017). Hence, the importance and usage of the methodology increased and it became a commonly used methodology for identifying rich sources of data, emerging into a method that combines qualitative and quantitative research (Johansson, 2007). When the research paradigm is insufficient for investigating complex real-world issues (Feagin et al., 1991) case study methodology is an ideal methodology. It can provide methods for complex, multidimensional problems when a holistic, in-depth investigation is needed (ibid). In this research, we choose to use a research case to answer SRQ2 and SRQ3. The assumption is that the learnings and findings of a digital twin implementation for a smart infrastructure asset would provide relevant information that may help other research projects in the future.

Similar to any other research project this study has several limitations. For instance, we have read many research articles but included the most relevant ones to this article, including digital twin architectures and implementations. While we have considered conducting a fair sample size and selection process it is inevitable to miss some relevant articles that are published during the time we have written this article. We have conducted one case study and choose a very specific infrastructure asset for this purpose. Therefore, it is very difficult to generalise the results related to the performance of the studied digital twin. For this reason, we have chosen the research question of the study that does not aim to provide generalisable answers to technology or performance-related questions but is

focused on the system design of the digital twin implementation. While we understand that this one case study will not be enough to represent a generalisable knowledge that would apply to any smart infrastructure digital twin project, we still believe that the learnings of this study and the proposed physical and cyber architectures would be beneficial to the domain.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Related Work

Early definitions of a digital twin, such as the one from Grieves & Vickers (2017), presented the concept with basic characteristics (Trauer et al., 2020) of a 'real space' and a 'virtual space' connected via data and information exchange (Grieves & Vickers, 2017). 'Real' is also later referred to as 'physical' and 'virtual' as 'cyber'. This division of physical and cyber parts is also seen as an evolution from Gelernter's (1991) "mirror worlds" concept which can be expressed as, "software programs... about to be joined by vast public software works that will revolutionise computing and transform society as a whole".

The most widely used definition of a digital twin is from NASA which states that the digital twin is an "integrated multi-physics, multi-scale, probabilistic simulation of a vehicle or system that uses the best available physical models, sensor updates, fleet history, etc., to mirror the life of its corresponding flying twin" (Shafto et al., 2012). A more recent definition in manufacturing defines the term as "... a digital representation of an active unique product [...] or unique product-service system [...] that comprises its selected characteristics, properties, conditions, and behaviours by means of models, information, and data within a single or even across multiple lifecycle phases" (Stark & Damerau, 2019). Digital twins in infrastructure is a new concept and there is no commonly accepted definition of the term. The Centre for Digital Built Britain defines it as "a realistic digital representation of assets, processes or systems in the built or natural environment" (Bolton et al., 2018).

Furthermore, several researchers have studied the potential of using big data in smart infrastructure, specifically in a smart grid or city context. Some studies focused on socio-economic problems and suggested using data to form collective awareness for creating innovative solutions (Pitt et al., 2013). Other studies looked at infrastructure from an efficiency perspective and included data resources from surveying, communication, geospatial and network applications to manage power consumption and operational resources (Al-hader & Rodzi, 2016). Recent literature is specifically rich when it comes to providing solutions to technical problems related to networking (Das et al., 2019; Idwan et al., 2017; Ota et al., 2017), monitoring (Alavi et al., 2019; Heaton et al., 2019) or data (Bowers et al., 2018; Gürdür, Raizer, et al., 2018).

At the same time, the literature on digital twins in infrastructure is still nascent. For instance, Gürdür Broo and Schooling (2020) suggested that the industry should address the challenges related to availability, accessibility, quality, volume, variety, and longevity of data by considering user-centric approaches, blending methodologies, and identifying the organisational needs. Sacks et al. (2020) argue that in the academic and popular literature of the built environment, many authors use the term digital twin simply (and naively) as a synonym for Building Information Modelling (BIM). While some researchers such as (Pan & Zhang, 2021) suggest ways to integrate BIM-based digital twins to facilitate data communication and exploration to better understand, predict, and optimise the physical operation, others such as (Boje et al., 2020) argues that "BIM lacks semantic completeness in areas such as control systems, including sensor networks, social systems, and urban artefacts beyond the scope of buildings, thus requiring a holistic, scalable semantic approach that factors in dynamic data at different levels." Similarly, some researchers (Borrmann et al., 2018) agree that digital twins for operation and maintenance in infrastructure are based largely on the building information models produced through their design and construction. The importance of differentiating 3D models and building information models from the digital twins is also highlighted by Tchana et al. (2019). They stated that the industry should move from the idea of 3D models (digital models) towards digital duplications (digital twins) of the infrastructure for effective lifecycle management. Furthermore, related to lifecycle management and sustainability of the future smart infrastructure systems, Gürdür Broo & Schooling, (2021) proposed a framework where data has been considered as an engineering tool for sustainable cyber-physical systems.

3.2. Digital Twin Architectures

Digital twin development for cyber-physical systems should be done in a systemic way where components or systems and their interactions with other components, devices or systems are well-thought from the beginning of the design process. Therefore, the first sub-research question of this study focuses on the literature on digital twin architectures. This section will summarise different architectural approaches that have been proposed by the scientific community.

One of the first architecture-related discussions on digital twins was published by Boschert & Rosen (2016) where the authors focused on the simulation aspect of digital twins for mechatronics. They have defined simulation as a merger for the physical and virtual world. The goal of the digital twin in this study is defined as “to prepare solutions for different but specific objectives and questions. The discussion on the architecture of a digital twin starts with the role of the architect. Boschert & Rosen (2016) defines four lifecycle phases for their principle approaches such as design, engineering, operation and service. The role of the digital town is to use the essential information originating from different information and technology systems and make it available throughout these phases. Therefore the digital twin architect is expected to describe the purpose(s) of the digital twin and derive a set of tasks that are derived from this goal. These tasks are later executed to answer specific questions. The final step in this approach is to the specification of the data and simulation model needs which builds the architecture of the digital twin for a concrete application and set of purposes.

Zhang et al., (2017) proposes a solution to rapid individualised designing of a production line. Similar to Boschert & Rosen, (2016), Zhang et al., (2017) defines the digital twin as a merger. In this study, the digital twin integrates physics-based system modelling and distributed real-time process data to generate an authoritative digital design of the system at the pre-production phase. The role of the digital twin is to provide engineering analysis capabilities and support the decision-making over the system designing and solution evaluation. They have adopted the idea of building reference models (Leng & Jiang, 2017) to produce a digital copy of a production line. Later, to address the critical gap between the twinning between the physical world and the virtual model, multi-view synchronisation and distributed semi-physical simulation and integration approaches are used. Finally, for optimisation of the performance, a multi-objective optimisation problem is defined and a decoupling algorithm is designed. While the system architecture is not defined explicitly, the coupling relationship of the multi-objective optimisation problem is designed as the coupling submits constraints that are collected from the physical environment, run the configuration variables, design parameters and operation parameters together with these constraints and solves the optimisation problem in the digital world before sending the optimal motion design back to the physical world.

One of the most accepted digital twin architectures is proposed by Alam & El Saddik, (2017) – C2PS as a digital twin architecture reference model for the cloud-based cyber-physical systems. The architecture model aims to support identifying various degrees of basic and hybrid computation-interaction modes. While the application of the architecture suggests using a Bayesian belief network and enables the system’s reconfiguration capabilities through fuzzy rule base with the Bayesian network, the reference architecture that has been proposed by the authors earlier (Alam et al., 2016) leverages the Sensing-as-a-Service model. In this model, things can communicate using direct physical connections or through the cyber layer using peer-to-peer inter-process communications. We have selected this model as a reference model to be used in our case study. Therefore, a more detailed explanation of the reference model is presented in Section 3.

Harper et al., (2019) focus on digital twin architectures and standards for the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) ecosystem. The authors state that the IIoT can be organized in tiers or layers where every layer may operate autonomously based on available data and services. Moreover, the communication between layers is interactions between architectural components, where some if not all the elements are digital twins. The study identifies six digital twin interactions such as interoperability, information model, data exchange, administration, synchronisation, and publishes/subscription. They also suggest nine evaluation criteria to assess these interactions. The finding of the study suggests that the architectural approach reduces Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) complexity, enhances privacy and security, and manages connectivity.

Another IIoT digital twin architecture is proposed by Souza et al., (2019). This architecture contains three main structures namely physical twin, IIoT gateway, and internal server. Physical twin includes the manufacturing processes which exchange data in regular and industrial communication protocols. IIoT gateway is the gateway that provides cross-communication between the physical twin and internal server through IIoT devices and wired connection. Lastly, the internal server is the computer that runs the digital twin and simulations providing connection inside and outside the workplace. This internal server has two versions. One is for the workplace, where the digital twin handles the critical operations and processes. The other one is open to interactions outside the workplace, where information about the processes, supply, and demand can be displayed depending on the user’s interests and privacy details.

Haße et al. (2019) focuses on key performance indicators (KPIs) and aims to use them as a basis for flexible and adaptive production systems. The goal of the study is to integrate real-time data processing with a digital twin, particularly in logistics. Inspiration comes from the ISO/IEC 2016 IoT architecture. The proposed Lambda architecture follows the end-to-end data management from data collection through data preparation up to data

visualisation. The three components of the architecture, therefore, are data acquisition, data processing and data visualisation. For data acquisition sensors, micro-controller and beacons are used. Through the WLAN network, this acquisition system is integrated with the data processing system. For the implementation of this data processing layer, a modified SMACK (Spark, Mesos, Akka, Cassandra, and Kafka) stack is used, which is a proven distributed big data stack for streaming data processing. Additionally, MQTT data broker Mosquitto and Java Spring Boot Framework are utilised to support the backend functions. The components communicate with the back end via representational state transfer (REST) API and the KPIs and digital descriptions of the physical objects are visualised on the frontend. Angular is used to create a component-based interface.

Gürdür, Raizer, et al., (2018) and Gürdür, Vulgarakis Feljan, et al., (2018) focused on knowledge representation for cyber-physical systems by exemplifying a data-driven architecture for complex logistics systems. In this study, the authors use federated digital twin implementation of an autonomous warehouse as a system of systems. The digital twin of this system of systems includes integration of several digital twins, such as Automated Storage and Retrieval Systems; robotics arms; and autonomous robots, and data streams from several additional components, such as cameras, conveyor belts, and humans that collaborate with the robots to accomplish tasks related to the business objectives. The authors suggested using a minimalistic data model through Open Services for Lifecycle Collaboration resource shapes to integrate the declarative and procedural knowledge of automated warehouse agents specified in Planning Domain Definition Language as a planner.

Another research on cloud-based digital twin applications is done by Hoebert et al., (2019). The framework architecture focuses on creating a twin directly from the semantical description of the system. Moreover, the digital twin supervises the physical asset's current actions based on the data that is received from the physical system. The cyber part of the system, the digital twin, analyses the current situation of the physical system, tests some alternative scenarios and gives relevant feedback when these scenarios result in an improved action. This architecture has four major components the semantic description of the robot system environment, a decision-making mechanism (planner), the digital environment (cyber) model and the physical system.

Another interesting architecture is proposed by Martinez-Velazquez et al., (2019) as a cardio twin. Cardio twin is a digital twin for healthcare and well-being which runs on the edge and aims to help in the event of an ischemic heart disease situation. The twin collects data from a network of body sensors and external sensors to integrate them with the medical records and social networks. This information gets processed and analysed to detect a stroke. Cardio twin has three parts: data sources, an AI-inference engine and a multimodal interaction layer. While the data sources gather the data from different types of sensors and databases, the AI-inference engine uses a pipeline where data fusion, standardisation, analytics and decision-making capabilities are deployed. The multimodal interaction layer delivers important information through visualisation techniques and enables smart services through communication networks.

Lu et al., (2020) presented digital twin development at a building and city level. The architecture of a dynamic city digital twin consists of five layers namely the data acquisition layer, transmission layer, digital modelling layer, model integration layer and services layer. This architecture shows commonalities with some of the architectures we have mentioned in this section such as the reference model that has been suggested by Alam et al., (2016), however, in this architecture, the integration efforts are concentrated on model-based approaches. Other digital twins are seen as part of the data acquisition layer where sub digital twins are imagined to provide necessary data/information/models when receiving a query from the city digital twin.

An open architecture model is proposed by Leng et al., (2020) as a solution to the need for high flexibility in manufacturing systems. The approach builds on the importance to have a standardised platform and extend it with various models and enable the manufacturing systems' modularity capabilities. To this end, these key enabling techniques are suggested; open-architecture standard platform and modularisation of machine tools, REST-based open interface of controls and self-adaptive clustering of industrial internet of things and digital twinning-driven simulations and automatic reconfiguration solutions.

Redelinghuys et al., (2020) proposed six-layer architecture for digital twin implementation of cyber-physical production systems. They build on the 5-level CPS architecture (5C architecture) of J. Lee et al., (2015). The 5Cs are connection, conversion, cyber, cognition and configuration. The proposed architecture from Redelinghuys et al., (2020) divides the physical twin into two layers; physical devices and data acquisition. Layer 3 is local data repositories, layer 4 is IoT gateway, layer 5 is cloud-based information repositories and layer 6 is emulation and simulation.

Finally, the reference architecture model for the digital twin as a service for Industry 4.0 is proposed by Aheleroff et al., (2021). This conceptual digital twin reference model has several layers; physical layer,

communication layer, digital layer, cyber layer, application layer and digital twin layers. The physical layer describes the physical assets, and the communication layer transfers the data to the digital layer. While the digital layer is recording the data in raw or different file formats, the cyber layer runs cloud processing and storage for building a dynamic data model. The application layer is where the data from smart sensors and IoT become knowledge and are made available. Lastly, the digital twin layer is the integration layer. The architecture also comments on a different level of value creation through integration. This level of integration is shown as an example of progress from digital model to digital shadow to digital twin to digital twin predictive.

4. Reference Architecture

In this study, smart infrastructure is seen as an example of cyber-physical systems. This perspective not only considers extending physical infrastructure assets with cyber abilities but also envisions building systems of systems integrations and services to address complex challenges that the infrastructure industry and assets are facing including efficiency, interoperability and carbon footprint.

Figure 1. Cloud-based cyber-physical systems architecture introduced in (Alam et al., 2016; Alam & El Saddik, 2017).

While we decided to use the cloud-based cyber-physical systems architecture that is proposed by Alam & El Saddik (2017), we have been inspired and intrigued by all of the architectures that have been presented in the earlier section. It has been clear that many spend an incredible amount of effort to find and define a generic, flexible, repeatable reference architecture and all had a unique approach in some aspects. At the same time, we realised that there were a lot of commonalities between these architectures.

Alam & El Saddik, (2017) present a digital twin architecture reference model (See Figure 1) for cloud-based CPS and named this architecture as C2PS. This architecture uses the standard CPS design concepts to incorporate cloud support. The architecture identifies the physical things as a first layer and builds cyber capabilities on top of these physical things. While the connections between the physical things are physical, in the second – cyber – layer connections are virtual. The architecture details separated data stores for each one of the cyber things. The third layer, peer to peer relation layer, is all about identifying relationships and linking the cyber things with each other through these relationships. The fourth layer is the intelligent service layer. These intelligent services are considered to have information about things, relations, data, ontology, and output. On top of all these layers, the system

administration and system usage layer sit as a top layer. Data consumption, service management, service integrator, data visualisation, and similar subsystems monitor, analyse, propagate and communicate the key performance indicators related to the cyber-physical system.

While building C2PS Alam & El Saddik (2017) find out that the current literature mostly described the integration of CPS and cloud support by using descriptive models, which lack a formal description of the three key characteristics of a CPS: computation, communication, and control. Therefore, they instead followed the state machine-based analytical design techniques to describe this integration. In this study, we will mainly focus on architecting data to support the operations of the digital twin through the C2PS reference architecture. Further state machine-based analytical design techniques will not be discussed here. Instead, we will focus on a case study, tool, and technologies to detail the design and implementation of a digital twin prototype for smart infrastructure as an example of a cyber-physical system.

5. Case Study

This section firstly describes the digital twin case study by presenting an activity diagram (See Figure X) which details the possible activities through sensing, data collection to file storage, analyses, data storage, and data visualisation. Then, the physical and cyber architecture of the system is described and data architecture is presented. And finally, the peer-to-peer relationships/integration and services are explained.

5.1. Description

In this case study, the main objective is to develop a digital twin of a physical asset. This particular physical asset is a Network Rail E-type steel half-through railway bridge with a single skew span of 26.84 metres and carries two rail lines within the West Coast Main Line near the city of Crewe in the United Kingdom. From the construction and instrumentation stages, the bridge is referred to as Intersection Bridge 5 (IB5) (Butler et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2019) and is part of the critical infrastructure in the rail upgrade and redevelopment project known as the Stafford Area Improvements Programme (Gibbons et al., 2015). Different stakeholders are engaged in the design and implementation of this digital twin project. These stakeholders can be listed as; structure engineers, software developers, data scientists, computer vision researchers, academic leads, and asset managers. The project is interdisciplinary in approach and the digital twin design and implementation decisions are discussed in frequent meetings with different stakeholders throughout the duration of the project.

The main structural elements of the IB5 bridge are two steel longitudinal girders, steel transversal beams, and a reinforced concrete (RC) deck. The longitudinal girders are precambered I-shaped steel-plate with 2.2 metres deep resting simply supported on ending RC abutments. The transversal beams provide lateral strength and stability and are 0.368 metres deep universal column (UC) sections. The deck is a 0.250 metres deep composite structure with a double layer of steel reinforcement. The interested readers are referred to (Butler et al., 2018; Lin et al., 2019) or an exhaustive description of the structural system and (Delgado et al., 2018) for a visualisation of the sensors' data within a BIM environment.

The sensing system installed in the IB5 bridge has distinctive monitoring characteristics due to the early service life for the system which was devised to be integral to the structural system. Hence this sensing system was designed and integrated during construction. Such early adoption of a sensing system from the conceptual design stage of the asset has been a missing link not only for the development of a digital twin but for the understanding of the undamaged structural integrity of the structure, which provides an invaluable baseline for posterior comparisons during the operational life of the system (Smith, 2015). This sensing instrumentation installed from the early stage consisted of fibre-optic-based strain and temperature Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors installed along the flanges of the main steel girders and the concrete deck. Additionally, extra sensing capabilities to detect rotation movements and vibrations have been deployed during the first half of 2021, along with a new centralised data acquisition system.

5.2. Physical Architecture

The physical components of the system have a structural health monitoring layer, data acquisition layer, local data repository, network, data processing layer, and data presentation layer. The structure health monitoring layer of the Staffordshire bridge (IB5) digital twin consists of several accelerometers, cameras, two different types of fibre optic sensors, axle detection system, laser rangefinders, temperature and humidity sensors. The data that is sensed by these components are synchronised, structured and acquired through devices such as optical sensing interrogator systems, microcontrollers and real-time embedded industrial controllers. Later, the data that has been transferred

from the health monitoring system and data acquisition devices firstly are stored in a mini-computer situated at the bridge site and then transferred through a 4G network to a file server and a cloud platform.

Figure 2. The physical architecture consists of structural health monitoring, data acquisition, local data repository, data transfer, data processing and data presentation components.

Figure 2 shows the details of the physical architecture where structure health monitoring, data acquisition, local data repository, data transfer, data processing and data presentation are shown separately and their relations are highlighted by the arrows stating the data flow in between these different layers.

Figure 3. Activity diagram which describes series of events and data flow from detection of the train to data collection, data transfer, analyses, data storage, and data visualisation.

Moreover, Figure 3 illustrates the activity diagram of the system. The details related to the analyses of the system is outside of the scope of this article. Therefore, we will not focus on the series of tools and algorithms related to that part which is represented by a grey rectangle in the middle of the figure. As the activity diagram summarises, the data acquisition process starts with the sensing activity. The systems start to save important data coming from different types of sensors (including camera) by firstly identifying the movement which is caused by a train passage. This data stream starts from 30 seconds before the train passes the bridge and stops 30 seconds

after. Different type of sensor data such as video recording, accelerometer data, FBG data, axel and wheel data, and temperature and humidity data is then synchronised and packed as a compressed file before being sent to the file server. At the same time, the data is extracted to a relational database on a cloud platform where relationships between bridge, train, sensing data, structural analyses including load and utilisation is structured in a certain way to be ready to be acquired by the analyses tools and applications.

The digital twin implementation which builds upon this physical architecture is designed to be used by stakeholders such as asset managers and structural engineers. However, the implementation of the system included researchers from data science, software development, civil engineering and signal processing fields. The cyber parts of the system include a series of software tools that are developed to assess structural behaviour by converting sensing data to statistical finite element and structural analysis models and visualising this information on the 3D model of the bridge for informing stakeholders about the behaviour of the bridge.

5.3. Cyber Architecture

The chosen software architecture builds on a cloud-based system composed of an array of individual Docker containers that is a standard unit of software that packages up code and all its dependencies so the application runs quickly and reliably from one computing environment to another (Docker, 2019). The software architecture is entirely powered by open-source programming languages and as previously mentioned the user interface is web-based.

There are several benefits to architect the digital twin solution this way, ranging from providing easy to use interface for the end-users that is operating system agnostic, to the centralised software maintenance where updates are immediately reflected across the system. The three main components are a back-end engine, an interactive front-end graphical user interface (GUI), and a framework that enables developers to use the REST interface to call commonly used functions of the implemented solution.

Figure 4 summarises the main components, interactions and the cyber architecture of the back-end of the digital twin. In addition to the physical instrumentation at the site, the back-end of the digital twin includes two key software abstractions, namely the Physical Instrumentation (PI) and the Virtual Instrumentation (VI). These two important software components belong to the Data Processing App and they are Python-based classes with equivalent attributes and methods that are devised to handle data exclusively from installed sensors and virtual frameworks, respectively. These two classes are responsible for handling all the data produced by the digital twin. For instance, a conventional Finite Element (FE) model of the bridge (Butler et al., 2018) would be a standalone VI object (VI 1). However, a more complex FE model, such as statFEM (Febrianto et al., 2021; Girolami et al., 2021), would be another VI object (VI 2) that depends on the PI object, due to the probabilistic nature of the statFEM framework that requires measured data.

Figure 4. Cyber architecture and data streams. The principal components are Site, Back-end, Front-end, and Fast-API.

The back-end of the digital twin's software is a collection of containers working in parallel on the cloud platform. In turn, a container is a collection of modules performing dedicated specific tasks, which can be launched and monitored individually. Figure 5. shows the module-level architecture of these principal containers and modules. The Main App (Container 1) is written in NodeJS. The main objective of this container is to orchestrate the behaviour of the remaining containers. The event-based nature of the Main App enables it to automatically handle the totality of events taking place in parallel, such as managing the incoming new raw data batches, data processing, feeding new data batched to multiple databases, updating PI and VI objects, and dealing with user requests from the front-end, among others. The Databases (Container 2) and Application programming interface (API) (Container 3) applications are essential for the communication of end-users, such as enabling researchers or

stakeholders to extract the stored raw and processed data. In other words, end-users have access to every stored data of the digital twin employing either sensor's data from the PI object or resulting data from existing VI objects. To this end, a Fast-API – to manage to GET and POST requests – together with a time-series optimised PostgreSQL – as an open-source database on the cloud – is adopted as an open-source database due to its high performance, lightness, and scalability. The Data Processing (Container 4) hosts the PI, VI, structural analysis, and data analysis modules (e.g. feature selection).

Figure 5. Back-end cyber architecture of the main containers and modules.

The front end is a web-based GUI that enables the user to interact with the digital twin. End-users have different levels of access permissions through an individual account to accommodate the security issues and varied user needs. Figure 6. shows the schema of the containers and modules of the front-end. As can be seen, two containers are dedicated for interactive 3D visualisations of the so-called PI and VI. Moreover, there is a container that is allocated for the visualisation of results produced by the structural analysis module of the back-end. Finally, the API hub offers a simple GUI to facilitate end-users' data requests.

Figure 6. The front-end software architecture of the main containers and modules.

5.4. Integration

One significant benefit of digital twins is being able to use them to consider data for making better decisions specific to not only one asset but integrated systems of systems. With this in mind, it is vital to design and develop the digital twin with this perspective. The current implementation of the IB5 digital twin does not have any connection with other digital twins. However, the design and implementation strategies included in the National Digital Twin Programme mentioned, for instance, Information Management Framework principles which are considered while the digital twin is designed. These principles include a consistent, clear understanding of what constitutes the world of digital twins as a foundation data model, the particular set of classes and the properties we will want to use to describe our digital twins as reference data library, and the protocols that will enable to manage sharing of data as part of an integration architecture (Hetherington & West, 2020).

Figure 7. Data flow from sensing to analyse to visualisation and finally to actions.

To this end, a list of key performance indicators, important visualisation needs, and analytical interests are collected from stakeholders that may later be used in discussions related to the integration of the IB5 digital twin with a network of digital twins. Integration does not only consider the sensing data that is deployed on the bridge but also considers data coming from other data streams to which the digital twin has connections. The overall aim of these integrations is ultimately to be able to gather information to act better – by informing better decision-making. This data model starts with sensing and continues as the data flows from one tool/system to another throughout the sense-making process. Sensing data are converted to analytical results through the analysis process, then the resulting data are visualised to inform actions. Some details of possible sensing data, analyses, visualisation interests and important actions are presented in Figure 7.

5.5. Services

An additional benefit from working with a digital twin and integrated digital twins is the ability to build new services based on these integrations. The service-oriented architectures have the potential to provide services to other systems by application components, through communication protocols over networks. These services turn the passive assets into interactive, living digital twins which collect data, run analytical models, drive actions and share information about all these processes enabling better decisions not only for an individual system but also the system of systems. Furthermore, the service-oriented digital twin implementation brings the possibilities of engaging different platforms to increase operational efficiency and opens up new ways of collaborations, information sharing and interdisciplinary ways of working to support more comprehensive analyses about smart infrastructure systems.

The service-oriented architecture consists of service interfaces, service implementations, service bus, and service consumers. The services can be either implemented as part of a digital twin where the data analytics, software components, and the applications run at the digital twin level and the results are shared with the service consumers, or the data related with the services can be shared with certain stakeholders on-demand to enable them

to derive and deliver services. The digital twin, in any case, is seen as a service provider and necessary security, privacy, safety, and similar concerns need to be agreed upon by all the parties.

Even though the IB5 digital twin's current implementation does not include integration with other digital twins or provides any service, the service-oriented architecture is found to be a beneficial way of designing the system. Providing services to managing safety, traffic, energy consumption, grid or sustainability decisions is certainly the next important step towards better smart infrastructure decisions.

6. Discussion

This study aimed to understand the applicability of the selected reference architecture to support the digital twin development of the Staffordshire bridges. The learning of this case study and detailed discussion on a series of challenges from different perspectives are discussed in this section. The next subsection mainly details the discussion around the systems perspective approach to the digital twin development. Subsection two focuses on the information perspective, subsection three discusses the organisational perspective and the fourth subsection briefly describes the limitations of the study.

6.1. Systems Perspective

One important consideration of the design and implementation of the IB5 digital twin was the systems perspective. The review and understanding of the existing reference architectures guided the system design and the selected reference architecture influenced the case study to not only consider having a digital representation of the physical asset but also to consider integration needs, imagine future service-oriented approaches and build interactive digital twins which can later be extended to be part of bigger digital twin system of systems.

It is important to take a systemic perspective from the very beginning of the project to the end of the project. Taking this perspective brings the stakeholders together to build the system architecture of the digital twin, share the information about the components of the system, discuss different stakeholders' requirements and expectations, identify key performance indicators that are important for stakeholders, and build flexible but also robust data models to implement the digital twin. While following a reference model when designing and implementing the digital twin is an important first step, the details of the digital twin functions, technologies that are used to build the cyber part of the system, and further consideration related to the integration and servitisation would not be possible without this systems perspective.

One of the important research questions presented at the beginning of this article concerned the design and implementation phases of digital twins in smart infrastructure. While there are common digital twin implementation-related considerations that have been previously, we also discovered a few smart infrastructure-related ones. For instance, the infrastructure industry is at a different stage when it comes to technology maturity compared to the manufacturing, automotive, and robotics industries where digital twin implementations are more common. Similarly, the construction and infrastructure industries are less likely to have systems engineers or systems thinkers when compared to some other industries. These differences affect design and implementation practices. For example, the health monitoring systems in this case study were not designed through the product development processes that are very common in computer science, mechanical engineering, and similar disciplines because the construction and infrastructure developments are not seen as products but as assets, and the health monitoring, sensing, data collection, software development, and similar activities are not part of the sector's mainstream practices. Additionally, the asset is generally constructed to serve a specific purpose as opposed to cyber-physical systems where the system does not only function for a specific purpose but also acts as a node in a bigger system, collects data, and communicates information.

6.2. Information Perspective

Another important research question that we aimed to answer with this study was regarding the software and data architecture of a digital twin in smart infrastructure assets. The detailed information about the software developed for this case study is described in the earlier sections. The most important considerations for this architecture can be listed as flexibility, openness, modularisation, and integration. Firstly, the IB5 digital twin had a flexible architecture operating system agnostic so any stakeholder with internet connectivity could use any web browser to reach the digital twin. Secondly, the software development tools and libraries are selected to be open source to eliminate vendor lock-in and provide simple license management, easier scaling and consolidating, more transparency, and lower software costs. Thirdly, throughout the architecture, we favoured the modularisation approach where we can concentrate to focus on developing one piece of software at a time, encapsulate functions and capabilities, decrease dependencies and increase reusability. Additionally, Docker containers are used to

provide a consistent and isolated environment, easy to test, roll back and deploy functionalities and improve collaboration and scaling. Lastly, the digital twin implementation builds on very well-known REST-based open interfaces and APIs to enable the integration of the digital twin with other digital twins in the future.

Additionally, the data management of the digital twin implementation has been part of many discussions during the design and development of the IB5 digital twin. Both relational and cloud-based databases, local and remote repositories are considered and the information from different data sources are planned to be stored as raw, analysed, and ready to be shared formats. Stakeholders discussed data availability, accessibility, challenges related to heterogeneity and quality. Even though the stakeholders coming from the construction, infrastructure and bridge engineering domains were not fully aware of the challenges related to the data and information management in several project meetings, these topics are presented and necessary knowledge is shared by the data scientist of the project. An extensive data management plan is prepared for the project and details about the data strategies and decisions are explained before and during project delivery. Furthermore, the reference digital twin has been found very beneficial to help to structure different data stores, their roles and helped to identify integration-related requirements and needs.

6.3. Organisational Perspective

The multidisciplinary nature of these studies has been both an opportunity to learn new domain knowledge and also a challenge to communicate various requirements coming from stakeholders which are explained in different terminologies. The last research question of this article that requires an answer is about this challenge; the non-technological aspects that affect the development and adoption of digital twins in smart infrastructure systems.

The digital twin development in infrastructure and even construction domains is in its early infancy and the classical civil engineering education and practices currently do not provide the necessary skill set for developing these digital twins. At the same time, since there are not so many projects that are developing digital twins for infrastructure assets, there are no well-defined processes or tools to help the development of digital twins. For these reasons, the projects are multidisciplinary efforts of civil engineers and computer scientists. This was no different in this study. While these multidisciplinary projects are great opportunities to learn from each other and develop knowledge in different domains, they are far from being perfect environments.

This study marked the first time that stakeholders came together to develop a digital twin. Similar to many research projects, the priorities and goals of stakeholders were different. However, perhaps what differed from many other projects was that at the intersection of computer science and civil engineering practices; the processes, terminology, the level of maturity of technology that is used and the data fluency of different stakeholders was found to be challenging when communicating these priorities. Hence, an important lesson from this study should be the value of approaching similar projects from the beginning with a systems perspective, to drive requirements at the beginning of the project, to identify the purpose and the goal of the digital twin very clearly and provide environments for discussions on the functionalities and capabilities of the digital twin as early as possible. Furthermore, we believe that industrial stakeholder engagement is vital to bridge the gap between a digital twin prototype and on scale digital twin implementations.

While the reference digital twin architectures may guide developers towards building digital twin prototypes, very few if any comment on these organisational, skills-related aspects of digital twin development. This study shows that non-technical considerations of digital twin development are as important as the technical ones, especially when teams are acquiring people outside of their domain for digital twin projects. The lack of literacy between different disciplines plays a big role when designing digital twins because a successful digital twin cannot be developed in a uni-disciplinary way.

7. Conclusion

This study aimed to understand how digital twins can be designed and developed to support better decision making for smart infrastructure assets. The study firstly reviewed the literature and identified relevant digital twin architectures that would help the design and development of a digital twin. The architectures came from a number of industries and exemplified how different digital twin prototypes may focus on various parts of the digital twin capabilities. Some focused on the detailed design of one specific digital twin while some others aimed to provide a reference architecture for a more generalisable digital twin design. One of the most popular and promising digital twin reference architecture is then selected to be used when designing a digital twin for a case study.

The infrastructure asset of the case study is an E-type steel half-through railway bridge. The digital twin design and implementation are completed in collaboration with several stakeholders who come from different backgrounds

and domains such as civil engineering, structural engineering and computer science. The physical asset is instrumented with several types of sensors to collect data for the purpose of structural health monitoring.

The digital twin implementation is described in detail from both physical and cyber perspectives. Important considerations of systems design, software architecture, information management and the future possibilities to operationalise this digital twin by integration and service design are discussed.

Significant findings from this study can be summarised under three subcategories, namely systems perspective, information perspective and organisational perspective. This case study shows the importance of having a systemic perspective when designing and implementing digital twins in smart infrastructure projects by highlighting the opportunities that digital twins may provide through integration with other systems of systems. Moreover, the experience of designing and implementing a digital twin demonstrated how vital it is to manage information. These data and information management practices are not only important to manage in relation to the sensing data but also understanding different viewpoints of the stakeholders and being able to provide a framework to consider their expectations from the digital twin. The multidisciplinary nature of this work has been found to be a crucial component of the organisational perspective. While there are many architectures that invite inspiration or even provide guidance to follow, there are not enough studies exploring how to deal with the organisational challenges related to digital twin implementations. This study shows that the real benefits of digital twins are not limited to developing a technology. In fact, having necessary organisational practices to deal with the knowledge gap between different stakeholders, building literacy to understand each other and having the necessary environment to enable collaborative and multidisciplinary ways of working is as important as the technical and technology-related challenges when designing digital twins.

Acknowledgement

This research forms part of the Centre for Digital Built Britain's (CDBB) work at the University of Cambridge within the Construction Innovation Hub (CIH) which brings together world-class expertise from the Manufacturing Technology Centre (MTC), BRE and CDBB to transform the UK construction sector. The Construction Innovation Hub is funded by UK Research and Innovation through the Industrial Strategy Fund. This research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 882550.

References

- Aheleroff, S., Xu, X., Zhong, R. Y., & Lu, Y. (2021). Digital Twin as a Service (DTaaS) in Industry 4.0: An Architecture Reference Model. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 47(October 2020), 101225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2020.101225>
- Al-hader, M., & Rodzi, A. (2016). The smart city infrastructure development & monitoring THE SMART CITY INFRASTRUCTURE Theoretical and Empirical Researches in Urban Management. *Theoretical and Empirical Research in Urban Management*, 2(11), 86–94.
- Alam, K. M., & El Saddik, A. (2017). C2PS: A digital twin architecture reference model for the cloud-based cyber-physical systems. *IEEE Access*, 5, 2050–2062. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2657006>
- Alam, K. M., Sopena, A., & Saddik, A. El. (2016). Design and Development of a Cloud Based Cyber-Physical Architecture for the Internet-of-Things. *Proceedings - 2015 IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia, ISM 2015*, 459–464. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISM.2015.96>
- Alavi, A. H., Hasni, H., Jiao, P., Aono, K., Lajnef, N., & Chakrabarty, S. (2019). *Self-charging and self-monitoring smart civil infrastructure systems: current practice and future trends*. *March 2019*, 34. <https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2513476>
- Batty, M. (2018). Digital twins. *Environment and Planning B: Urban Analytics and City Science*, 45(5), 817–820. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2399808318796416>
- Boje, C., Guerriero, A., Kubicki, S., & Rezgui, Y. (2020). Towards a semantic Construction Digital Twin: Directions for future research. *Automation in Construction*, 114(January), 103179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103179>
- Bolton, R. N., McColl-Kennedy, J. R., Cheung, L., Gallan, A., Orsingher, C., Witell, L., & Zaki, M. (2018). Customer Experience Challenges: Bringing Together Digital, Physical and Social Realms. *Journal of Service Management*.
- Borrmann, A., König, M., Koch, C., & Beetz, J. (2018). Building Information Modeling – Why? What? How? In *Building information modeling*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ij3dim.2012100101>
- Boschert, S., & Rosen, R. (2016). Digital twin—the simulation aspect. *Mechatronic Futures: Challenges and Solutions for Mechatronic Systems and Their Designers*, 59–74.
- Bowers, K., Buscher, V., Dentten, R., Edwards, M., England, J., Enzer, M., Parlikad, A. K., & Schooling, J. (2018). *Smart Infrastructure: Getting more from strategic assets*. <https://www-smartinfrastucture.eng.cam.ac.uk/files/the-smart-infrastructure-paper>
- Butler, L. J., Lin, W., Xu, J., Gibbons, N., Elshafie, M. Z. E. B., & Middleton, C. R. (2018). Monitoring, modeling, and assessment of a self-sensing railway bridge during construction. *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, 23(10), 4018076.
- Das, A., Gupta, R., & Chakraborty, S. (2019). Motivating In-network Fusion for Smart Infrastructure Monitoring. *2019 11th International*

Conference on Communication Systems and Networks, COMSNETS 2019, 513–516.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/COMSNETS.2019.8711204>

- Delgado, J. M. D., Butler, L., Brilakis, I., Elshafie, M., & Middleton, C. (2018). *Structural performance monitoring using a dynamic data-driven BIM environment*.
- Docker. (2019). *What is a Container? | App Containerization*. Docker.Com. <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container>
- Feagin, J. R., Orum, A. M., & Sjoberg, G. (1991). *A case for the case study*. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press Books.
- Febrianto, E., Butler, L., Girolami, M., & Cirak, F. (2021). A Self-Sensing Digital Twin of a Railway Bridge using the Statistical Finite Element Method. *ArXiv Preprint ArXiv:2103.13729*.
- Gelernter, D. (1991). *Mirror Worlds*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780195068122.001.0001>
- Gibbons, N., Butler, L. J., Williamson, M., Ellwood, A., Platt, R., Oliver, J., Henwood, M., Holland, P., Dirar, S., Arthurs, S., & others. (2015). *Monitoring the early age behaviour of prestressed concrete beams using fibre optic sensors*.
- Girolami, M., Febrianto, E., Yin, G., & Cirak, F. (2021). The statistical finite element method (statFEM) for coherent synthesis of observation data and model predictions. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 375, 113533.
- Glaessgen, E. H., & Stargel, D. S. (2012). The digital twin paradigm for future NASA and U.S. Air force vehicles. *Collection of Technical Papers - AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2012-1818>
- Grieves, M., & Vickers, J. (2017). Digital Twin: Mitigating Unpredictable, Undesirable Emergent Behavior in Complex Systems. In *Transdisciplinary Perspectives on Complex Systems* (Issue August, pp. 85–113). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-38756-7_4
- Gürdür Broo, D., & Schooling, J. (2020). Towards Data-centric Decision Making for Smart Infrastructure: Data and Its Challenges. *4th IFAC Workshop on Advanced Maintenance Engineering, Services and Technologies*.
- Gürdür Broo, D., & Schooling, J. (2021). A Framework for Using Data as an Engineering Tool for Sustainable Cyber-Physical Systems. *IEEE Access*, 9, 22876–22882. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3055652>
- Gürdür, D. (2017). *Making Interoperability Visible: A Novel Approach to Understand Interoperability in Cyber-Physical Systems Toolchains*. KTH Royal Institute of Technology.
- Gürdür, D., Raizer, K., & El-Khoury, J. (2018). Data Visualization Support for Complex Logistics Operations and Cyber-physical Systems. *13th International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications*.
- Gürdür, D., Vulgarakis Feljan, A., El-Khoury, J., Kumar Mohalik, S., Badrinath, R., Pradeep Mujumdar, A., & Fersman, E. (2018). Knowledge Representation of Cyber-physical Systems for Monitoring Purpose. *Procedia CIRP*, 72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2018.03.018>
- Harper, K. E., Ganz, C., & Malakuti, S. (2019). Digital Twin Architecture and Standards. *IIC Journal of Innovation*, December, 0–12.
- HaBe, H., Li, B., Weißenberg, N., Cirullies, J., & Otto, B. (2019). Digital Twin for Real-Time Data Processing in Logistics. *Artificial Intelligence and Digital Transformation in Supply Chain Management (Proceedings of the Hamburg International Conference of Logistics (HICL), 27)*, 27(February 2020), 0–1. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15480/882.2462>ThisVersionisavailableat:<http://hdl.handle.net/10419/209367><https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/www.econstor.eu>
- Heaton, J., Parlikad, A. K., & Schooling, J. (2019). Design and development of BIM models to support operations and maintenance. *Computers in Industry*, 111, 172–186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2019.08.001>
- Hetherington, J., & West, M. (2020). *The pathway towards an Information Management Framework - A 'Commons' for Digital Built Britain*. 30. <https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/handle/1810/305579>
- Hoebert, T., Lepuschitz, W., List, E., & Merdan, M. (2019). *Cloud-Based Digital Twin for Industrial Robotics*. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-27878-6_9
- Idwan, S., Zubairi, J. A., & Mahmood, I. (2017). *Smart Solutions for Smart Cities: Using Wireless Sensor Network for Smart Dumpster Management*. October, 493–497. <https://doi.org/10.1109/cts.2016.0092>
- Johansson, R. (2007). On Case Study Methodology. *Open House International*, 32(3), 48–54. <https://doi.org/10.1108/OHI-03-2007-B0006>
- Lee, E. A., & Seshia, S. A. (2016). *Introduction to Embedded Systems, A Cyber-Physical Systems Approach*. MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.1007/71006>
- Lee, J., Bagheri, B., & Kao, H. A. (2015). A Cyber-Physical Systems architecture for Industry 4.0-based manufacturing systems. *Manufacturing Letters*, 3, 18–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mfglet.2014.12.001>
- Leng, J., & Jiang, P. (2017). Granular computing-based development of service process reference models in social manufacturing contexts. *Concurrent Engineering*, 25(2), 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1063293X166666312>
- Leng, J., Liu, Q., Ye, S., Jing, J., Wang, Y., Zhang, C., Zhang, D., & Chen, X. (2020). Digital twin-driven rapid reconfiguration of the automated manufacturing system via an open architecture model. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 63(March 2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2019.101895>
- Lin, W., Butler, L. J., Elshafie, M. Z. E. B., & Middleton, C. R. (2019). Performance assessment of a newly constructed skewed half-through railway bridge using integrated sensing. *Journal of Bridge Engineering*, 24(1), 4018107.
- Lu, Y., Liu, C., Wang, K. I. K., Huang, H., & Xu, X. (2020). Digital Twin-driven smart manufacturing: Connotation, reference model, applications and research issues. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 61(August 2019), 101837.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2019.101837>

- Martinez-Velazquez, R., Gamez, R., & Saddik, A. El. (2019). Cardio Twin: A Digital Twin of the human heart running on the edge. *Medical Measurements and Applications, MeMeA 2019 - Symposium Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MeMeA.2019.8802162>
- Ota, K., Kumrai, T., Dong, M., Kishigami, J., & Guo, M. (2017). Smart Infrastructure Design for Smart Cities. *IT Professional*, 19(5), 42–49. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MITP.2017.3680957>
- Pan, Y., & Zhang, L. (2021). A BIM-data mining integrated digital twin framework for advanced project management. *Automation in Construction*, 124(January). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103564>
- Pitt, J., Bourazeri, A., Nowak, A., Roszczynska-Kurasinska, M., Rychwalska, A., Rodriguez Santiago, I., Lopez Sanchez, M., Florea, M., & Sanduleac, M. (2013). Transforming big data into collective awareness. *Computer*, 46(6), 40–45. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2013.153>
- Qi, Q., & Tao, F. (2018). Digital Twin and Big Data Towards Smart Manufacturing and Industry 4.0: 360 Degree Comparison. *IEEE Access*, 6, 3585–3593. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2793265>
- Redelinghuys, A. J. H., Basson, A. H., & Kruger, K. (2020). A six-layer architecture for the digital twin: a manufacturing case study implementation. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 31(6), 1383–1402. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10845-019-01516-6>
- Rice, J. A., Mechitov, K., Sim, S.-H., Nagayama, T., Jang, S., Kim, R., Spencer, B. F. J., Agha, G., & Fujino, Y. (2010). Flexible smart sensor framework for autonomous structural health monitoring. *Smart Structures and Systems*, 6(5_6), 423–438. https://doi.org/10.12989/sss.2010.6.5_6.423
- Rudrappa, S. G. (2017). *Architecture To Bridge Physical world to Virtual Digital World*. Medium. <https://medium.com/@shivakumar.goniwada/architecture-to-bridge-physical-world-to-virtual-digital-world-d55ecbe93b85>
- Sacks, R., Brilakis, I., Pikas, E., Xie, H. S., & Girolami, M. (2020). Construction with digital twin information systems. *Data-Centric Engineering*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dce.2020.16>
- Schleich, B., Anwer, N., Mathieu, L., & Wartzack, S. (2017). Shaping the digital twin for design and production engineering. *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, 66(1), 141–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cirp.2017.04.040>
- Shafto, M., Conroy, M., Doyle, R., Glaessgen, E., Kemp, C., LeMoigne, J., & Wang, L. (2012). Modeling, Simulation, information Technology & Processing Roadmap. *Technology Area 11*, 1–38.
- Smith, I. F. C. (2015). Grand challenges of structural sensing. *Frontiers in Built Environment*, 1, 19.
- Souza, V., Cruz, R., Silva, W., Lins, S., & Lucena, V. (2019). A Digital Twin Architecture Based on the Industrial Internet of Things Technologies. *2019 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics, ICCE 2019*, 9–10. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCE.2019.8662081>
- Stark, R., & Damerau, T. (2019). Digital twin. *CIRP Encyclopedia of Production Engineering*, 66, 1–8.
- Tao, F., Cheng, J., Qi, Q., Zhang, M., Zhang, H., & Sui, F. (2018). Digital twin-driven product design, manufacturing and service with big data. *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 94(9–12), 3563–3576. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-017-0233-1>
- Tchana, Y., Ducellier, G., & Remy, S. (2019). Designing a unique Digital Twin for linear infrastructures lifecycle management. *Procedia CIRP*, 84, 545–549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2019.04.176>
- Trauer, J., Schweigert-Recksiek, S., Okamoto, L. O., Spreitzer, K., Mörtl, M., & Zimmermann, M. (2020). Data-driven engineering definitions and insights from an industrial case study for a new approach in technical product development. *Proceedings of the NordDesign 2020 Conference, NordDesign 2020*, 757–766. <https://doi.org/10.35199/norddesign2020.46>
- XMPRO. (2019). *The Ultimate Guide To Digital Marketing* (Vol. 53, Issue 9). <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- Zhang, H., Liu, Q., Chen, X., Zhang, D., & Leng, J. (2017). A Digital Twin-Based Approach for Designing and Multi-Objective Optimization of Hollow Glass Production Line. *IEEE Access*, 5, 26901–26911. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2766453>